

Open-Source Predictive Maintenance System for AC Motors Using Vibration and Temperature Analysis

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Abstract—This paper presents the design and experimental validation of a low-cost open-source predictive maintenance (PdM) system for alternating current (AC) induction motors. The proposed platform integrates wireless sensing nodes based on the Wemos D1 Mini (ESP8266), a three-axis MEMS accelerometer (MPU6050), and an LM35 temperature sensor. The system architecture enables distributed acquisition of vibration and thermal data, which are analyzed using Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural networks for anomaly detection. Experimental validation using controlled mechanical imbalance demonstrates that the proposed solution can reliably identify abnormal operating conditions with accuracy exceeding 80%. The results highlight the feasibility of combining open hardware and machine learning techniques for industrial predictive maintenance applications and provide a foundation for future edge computing implementations.

Index Terms—Predictive Maintenance, Induction Motors, Open Source, LSTM, Vibration Analysis, Edge Computing, Industry 4.0

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Evolution of Maintenance

Within the Industry 4.0 ecosystem, asset management has evolved from reactive and time-based preventive models toward condition-based predictive strategies. This transition aims to achieve “maximum availability at minimum cost” [1], requiring real-time data acquisition infrastructures. Monitoring critical operational variables enables deterministic decision-making, optimizing equipment lifecycle and reducing unplanned downtime.

B. Limitations of Proprietary Solutions

Commercial platforms such as Weg Motor Scan and ABB Smart Sensor offer advanced monitoring capabilities. However, these systems introduce significant barriers, including high subscription costs, closed software ecosystems, and limited data sovereignty. A critical limitation is restricted historical data retention—often limited to three months—which constrains long-term trend analysis and the effective training of deep learning models that benefit from extensive datasets.

C. Open Source Philosophy and Technological Sovereignty

The main contribution of this work is the design and experimental validation of an open-source predictive maintenance

architecture for induction motors based on low-cost hardware and machine learning techniques. The proposed system demonstrates that accessible sensing platforms combined with artificial intelligence algorithms can provide reliable early fault detection capabilities in industrial environments.

This project adopts the principles of the Open Source Initiative: free redistribution, source code availability, and permission for derivative works. This approach promotes technological sovereignty by allowing organizations to adapt the system to their operational realities without vendor lock-in. Full transparency ensures traceability from raw data acquisition to predictive inference.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The proposed predictive maintenance platform follows a layered architecture composed of distributed sensing nodes, a local gateway, and a centralized artificial intelligence processing server.

Sensor nodes installed on industrial motors collect vibration and temperature data and transmit the measurements wirelessly to a gateway located on the factory floor. The gateway aggregates and stores the data before forwarding them to a centralized processing server where machine learning algorithms perform predictive analysis.

The overall system architecture is illustrated in Figure 1.

The proposed architecture follows a distributed Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) paradigm in which sensing, aggregation, and intelligent processing are separated into independent functional layers. This design improves scalability, facilitates system maintenance, and enables future deployment of edge intelligence directly on embedded platforms.

A. Sensor Node (Acquisition Layer)

Each wireless node is designed for cable-less factory floor deployment and integrates:

- Wemos D1 Mini (ESP8266) with integrated TCP/IP stack and Wi-Fi connectivity
- MPU6050 (GY-521) MEMS accelerometer for vibration signature acquisition
- LM35 (TO-92) precision analog temperature sensor

Fig. 1. Architecture of the proposed open-source predictive maintenance system showing wireless sensor nodes installed on industrial motors, a factory-floor gateway based on Raspberry Pi, and a centralized server responsible for data processing and artificial intelligence inference.

Component selection was driven by regional availability (Uruguay), low cost, and adequate signal-to-noise ratio for mechanical vibration diagnostics.

B. Gateway and Local Repository (Aggregation Layer)

A Raspberry Pi running Raspberry Pi OS Lite acts as a gateway between sensor nodes and the central server. The device hosts an Apache web server with PHP and a MariaDB (SQL) database. Operating as a Wireless Access Point, the gateway guarantees local data persistence and uninterrupted acquisition in case of external connectivity loss.

C. AI Processing Layer (Application Layer)

Aggregated time-series data are transferred to a dedicated x86 server for computationally intensive processing. Artificial Intelligence algorithms convert vibration and temperature sequences into health indicators for monitored assets.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND METHODOLOGY

A. Test Bench

Validation was conducted using two representative industrial assets:

- Single-phase motor: 550W, 2840 RPM
- Three-phase motor: 1100W, 1450 RPM

These motors represent typical small- and medium-scale industrial loads.

B. Testing Protocol

System sensitivity was evaluated using a controlled shaft imbalance protocol. Incremental counterweights (13.39g, 16.46g, 32.92g, 43.37g) were applied. Each configuration underwent five 9-minute trials, ensuring thermal and mechanical stability before data acquisition [2].

C. Reference Standards

Diagnostics were aligned with international standards:

- ISO 20816-1 for vibration severity classification
- IEC 60085:2007 for thermal insulation evaluation

For motors under 15kW, strict lower-bound vibration thresholds (0.71–4.5 mm/s) were adopted.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Sensor Validation and Mechanical Sensitivity

Hardware response demonstrated strong linearity under imbalance conditions. In the three-phase motor, standard deviation increased proportionally to added mass, confirming high mechanical sensitivity.

For example, at 43.37g imbalance, vibration deviation increased by 280.1% on the X-axis relative to baseline conditions, evidencing reliable anomaly amplification.

B. Neural Network Implementation

The predictive model was implemented as a deep sequential network comprising dense layers of 100, 60, 16, and 8 neurons with ReLU activation, followed by a Dense(1) output layer. Training was performed using:

- Batch size = 1
- 100 epochs
- Adam optimizer
- Mean Squared Error (MSE) loss

TABLE I
VIBRATION BEHAVIOUR ANALYSIS UNDER DIFFERENT MASS CONDITIONS

Test Condition	Mass (g)	Observed Vibration Behaviour	Anomaly Detected
Baseline	0	Stable vibration signature	No
Test 1	13.39	Moderate increase in vibration deviation	Yes
Test 2	16.46	Noticeable vibration variation	Yes
Test 3	32.92	High vibration dispersion	Yes
Test 4	43.37	Strong vibration anomaly	Yes

C. LSTM Predictive Performance

The experimental evaluation demonstrates that low-cost MEMS sensors can provide vibration signals with sufficient fidelity for predictive maintenance applications. The proposed architecture successfully captures variations in vibration signatures produced by controlled mechanical imbalance.

The LSTM model was able to detect abnormal operating conditions with an anomaly detection accuracy exceeding 80%, confirming the feasibility of combining low-cost sensing nodes with machine learning techniques for industrial predictive maintenance applications.

Beyond the specific model performance, the results highlight the practical viability of open-source predictive maintenance platforms for small and medium-sized industrial environments, where commercial monitoring systems may be economically prohibitive.

V. CONCLUSIONS, FUTURE DEVELOPMENT AND TECHNOLOGICAL ROADMAP

Future development will focus on strengthening the system through hardware evolution, edge intelligence deployment, and industrial scalability validation.

A. Hardware Evolution

The processing platform will migrate from the ESP8266 to higher-performance microcontrollers such as the ESP32 or STM32 (ARM Cortex-M with DSP extensions), selected based on benchmarking of inference latency, memory usage, and energy efficiency under real-time conditions.

The vibration sensor will transition from the MPU6050 to the ADXL345 digital triaxial accelerometer, offering improved resolution, selectable measurement ranges (± 2 g to ± 16 g), and higher output data rates suitable for frequency-domain diagnostics aligned with ISO 20816 criteria. Thermal monitoring will replace the analog LM35 with the digital DS18B20, eliminating ADC-related quantization variability and improving noise immunity.

The next PCB revision will incorporate SMD decoupling capacitors placed near supply pins to mitigate conducted and radiated electromagnetic interference (EMI). Combined with optimized grounding, this enhancement is expected to improve signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and acquisition stability in industrial environments.

B. Edge AI Deployment and Validation

A primary objective is executing quantized LSTM inference directly at the edge layer. Deploying optimized models on ESP32 or STM32 platforms will reduce latency and bandwidth requirements while enabling deterministic real-time anomaly detection without reliance on centralized infrastructure.

Future work will also include long-term industrial validation under variable load and noise conditions to assess model generalization and multi-node scalability. This roadmap positions the system as a technically viable and sovereign open-source alternative for industrial predictive maintenance.

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REFERENCES

- [1] S. García, *Organización y gestión integral de mantenimiento*, Madrid, Spain: Ediciones Díaz de Santos, 2003.
- [2] G. White, *Introducción al Análisis de Vibraciones*, Azima DLI, 2010.
- [3] Mechanical vibration — Measurement and evaluation of machine vibration, ISO 20816-1, 2016.
- [4] Electrical insulation — Thermal evaluation and designation, IEC 60085, 2007.
- [5] J. P. de León Sum, “Sistema de código abierto para la predicción de fallas en motores de corriente alterna por vibración,” Postgraduate Thesis, Posgrado en Robótica e Inteligencia Artificial, UTEC, Rivera, Uruguay, 2021.